

THE FUTURE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MEDICINE: PRESENT REALITIES AND FUTURE CONSIDERATIONS IN CARDIOLOGY, RADIOLOGY AND OPHTHALMOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming an increasingly essential part of medicine today and will continue to grow in its applications to the field. Typical applications of AI in medicine include patient diagnosis, drug research and discovery, improving patient-physician interactions, transcribing medical records and prescriptions, and providing remote treatment. Contemporary algorithms and techniques have achieved accuracy levels comparable to those of human specialists or better and often perform tasks more swiftly. It may only be a matter of time before AI will replace humans in specific medical roles. This article examines how AI is used in the modern day medical field and what the future of medicine and AI will likely evolve into. This study finds that AI is set to be the new physician's assistant and even replace the role of the physician in certain contexts.

WHAT WE ALREADY KNOW:

- *We already know that there will be an increase in the use of AI technologies in the medical field, which has been shown by the increase of the use of AI by present-day doctors.*
- *AI technologies are being developed but many doctors do not know how to effectively utilize these powerful tools to improve their clinical practice.*

WHAT THIS ARTICLE ADDS:

- *This article will show how AI is most likely to progress and give an overview of the current advances of AI in medicine, focusing on the fields of cardiology, radiology and ophthalmology.*

The Future of Artificial Intelligence in Medicine: Present Realities and Future Considerations in Cardiology, Radiology and Ophthalmology

- *It will show what current technologies are advancing, for both physician and patient use, to improve the healthcare sector as a whole and lead to improved and healthier lives for all.*

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Radiology, Ophthalmology, Cardiology, Healthcare, Technology

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1. Introduction

AI is being used in the healthcare sector, and people are getting used to it. The healthcare AI market is increasing and is expected to reach \$6.6 billion by 2021. Advances in learning algorithms, computing power, and the availability of large datasets are driving the increasing role of AI in medicine and healthcare. Learning algorithms are helping more in enabling new ways for more precise diagnostics and treatment. AI applications promise better disease identification and patient care with more efficiency and effectiveness. They analyze and work on the data that they get from Electronic Medical Records of different hospitals or from wearable health trackers [1].

AI can assist physicians in improving patient care quality, diagnosis and treatment, handle repetitive tasks, manage large data sets, and by analyzing them, provide decision support to reduce errors. Estimates suggest AI could improve patient outcomes by 30% - 40% and make the treatment half the cost [1]. Experts believe AI can improve all the healthcare sectors outstandingly. However, they are still in the early stages of adoption by the human [1].

AI algorithms have a promising influence as a specialization in almost all sectors like radiology, pathology, neurology, ophthalmology, cancer detection and cardiology [1].

This new innovation also comes with many questions like: “Will AI eventually replace certain medical professionals, like radiologists, or will it help them become more efficient? Will humans trust AI with their health?” This paper examines the possible applications of artificial intelligence (AI) in medicine. It explores the idea that AI might eventually replace sure doctors or, at least, work as their helping hand.

Background

Machine learning models have demonstrated significant success in utilizing computer vision techniques to diagnose various eye diseases. Studies have utilized supervised machine learning classifiers to differentiate healthy eyes from those with glaucoma based on Artificial intelligence (AI) application to patient diagnosis has advanced significantly, especially in dermatology [5,6]. Scientists like Esteva et al. and Hekler et al. have created classification models using medical imaging of infected patients to identify various skin diseases, such as psoriasis and skin cancer [3,4]. After training on more than 129,450 pictures, it was found that deep convolutional neural network (DCNN) can give a diagnosis which is more accurate than what 21 dermatologists with board certification can give. According to the study, dermatologists require substantial medical training to achieve equivalent accuracy, whereas AI can complete these duties faster.

AI and patient prognosis have also been studied extensively. For example, using 128,175 retinal fundus pictures, researchers at Google [2] constructed and trained a DCNN to categorize images as diabetic retinopathy and macular edema for persons with diabetes. The existence of such an AI model has several benefits, some of them are:

- Automated diabetic retinopathy grading improves diagnostic efficiency by quickly diagnosing many patients.
- AI acts as an additional ophthalmologist's viewpoint.
- Extensive coverage of screening initiatives that lower entry barriers.
- Early detection of diabetic retinopathy is essential because the model can analyze pictures at a granular level, something a human ophthalmologist cannot accomplish.

Significant progress has been achieved in using AI algorithms for personalized therapy choices and medication discovery [2]. Many organizations focus on using machine-learning algorithms to evaluate human genetic data and find affordable medications to treat neurological conditions such as ALS, Alzheimer's, and Parkinson's.

AI-based technologies are used in healthcare industries to improve patient care, patient experience, and physician assistance. Few companies have developed systems that can provide round-the-clock assistance with clinical problems about:

- The AI technology can instantly determine which doctors are on call and book the next available appointment. It can also search across several scheduling platforms at various institutions.
- Answering users' concerns about the availability of medications, the price of a medicine, or any alternative available for a particular medicine.
- Clinicians may benefit from using mobile apps. This can improve a hospital's workflow by searching for a hospital's protocol, the clinic's instruments, or the pharmacy's medicines.

AI Devices

AI gadgets are mainly divided into two groups. Machine learning (ML) approaches that analyze structured data, such as genetic, imaging, and EP data, fall under the first group.

- ML techniques identify the patient's different characteristics and group them or predict the symptoms of a particular disease.
- Natural language processing (NLP) techniques fall into the second group. These techniques extract information from unstructured data, such as medical journals or clinical notes, and use it to organize medical data.

NLP methods aim to convert texts into structured data that machines understand so that ML algorithms can use them [36]. Figure 1's flow chart shows the road map from clinical data production via NLP data enrichment and ML data analysis to clinical decision-making. Clinical interventions are included at the start or end of the route map. Despite the strength of AI techniques, clinical issues must ultimately determine how they are used to enhance clinical practice.

The Future of Artificial Intelligence in Medicine: Present Realities and Future Considerations in Cardiology, Radiology and Ophthalmology

Figure 1. The path from the creation of clinical data to data enrichment through NLP, data analysis through machine learning, and finally, clinical decision-making. (EP stands for electrophysiological; EMR for electronic medical record) [36].

2. Improving Healthcare Efficacy and Precision

AI is transforming the healthcare sector across a spectrum by increasing the precision and efficacy of patient care. AI technologies provide unimaginable capacities for pattern recognition, data processing, and decision-making, from improving diagnosis to maximizing treatment strategies [7].

Automated Data Analysis: AI algorithms expertly analyze vast amounts of patient data, enabling healthcare providers to swiftly and reliably extract valuable insights. This automated data processing method can efficiently process even complex medical records, images, lab test results, or genomic information. This computerized analysis accelerates the discovery of patterns, connections, and anomalies that might have been overlooked previously. This system also helped doctors do advanced treatments on patients by identifying their complicated problems. Below is a figure showing how doctors and patients use the automated data analysis system.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the tele monitoring health scenario.

Predictive Analytics and Early Intervention: AI-powered predictive analytics enables identifying patients at a high risk of developing particular illnesses. Predictive analytics also helps with population health management, allowing medical practitioners to efficiently distribute resources and conduct preventative measures on a broader scale. By analyzing patient data and community health patterns, AI systems can predict the type of disease and its early symptoms and treat the patient beforehand for the disease. This proactive strategy improves patient outcomes by permitting timely treatment, reducing the likelihood of complications, and optimizing resource utilization [8].

Robotics and Automation in Surgery: Integrating AI-powered robotics and automation into surgery has transformed procedures by boosting precision & improving patient results. AI-controlled robots enhance visualization, skill, and control during complex surgeries. They lead to less invasiveness, fewer complications, and faster recovery. AI algorithms also assist in planning by stimulating surgeries and predicting challenges. This technological advancement represents a significant shift in surgical practice, elevating outcomes and expanding the capabilities of the operating room [9].

Workflow Optimization and Operational Efficiency: AI algorithms facilitate resource allocation, patient triage, and bed management, ensuring optimal utilization of healthcare facilities. Allowing AI to handle repetitive tasks gives healthcare personnel more time to focus on the patient. AI technology enhances operational efficiency and streamlines healthcare workflows. Intelligent automation reduces manual tasks and errors by optimizing administrative processes such as record-keeping, billing, and scheduling [10].

The application of AI algorithms in medicine has advanced recently.

Medical industries have started to utilize AI-based tools, even though AI systems have consistently demonstrated their effectiveness in various retrospective medical studies. However, critics point out that AI systems are less valuable than retroactive data suggests [56]. They must be more active or complex to help the medical industries [57]. Or they might introduce unanticipated issues via their interaction with humans and AIs. Filtering and cleaning are also applied to retrospective in silico datasets, which might reduce their representativeness of actual medical practice.

The gap between theoretical and practical applications of AI in healthcare can be addressed through prospective research and randomized controlled trials (RCTs) [58], which can demonstrate the measurable benefits of AI in real-world settings. Recent RCTs have tested AI systems for various medical applications, such as managing insulin dosage and monitoring intraoperative hypotension. These studies often use additional criteria beyond accuracy to evaluate effectiveness. To improve the research and sharing of AI's value in medicine. guidelines like AI-specific additions to SPIRIT and CONSORT and future guidelines such as STARD-AI aim to standardize the reporting and evaluation of medical AI technologies [60,61].

With administrative and regulatory support, AI tools have recently moved from testing to development. The Center for Medicare and Medicaid Services has facilitated AI integration by reimbursing two AI systems used in medical image diagnosis. In 2020, a study also highlighted that FDA approval for AI products, especially using ML, has increased. Although these are only clearances that have not been fully approved, Despite these advancements, there is still a need for better transparency and validation standards. Which also includes proof of measurable impacts on clinical outcomes to build trust in medical AI systems.

AI has started to change the healthcare industry in many ways, but there are places where AI has already begun to make changes or scientists have started to think about it. Table 1 below shows some examples and their uses [69].

Table 1. AI examples in healthcare [69].

Name of AI-based tools	Purpose
Seizure-detecting smart bracelets	AI-operated wristbands are used to detect a general tonic-clonic seizure.
Emergency detection	These AI-based devices are faster than clinicians. They can detect sepsis 6 hours before clinicians.
Detecting arrhythmias	AI released super portable & affordable apps that help patients get an ECG just by sitting at home.
Skin checking app	They are AI-based apps used to check skin diseases. By clicking pictures of the affected area, they identify them even before dermatologists.
Drug discovery	AI alters the drug production technique by making it cheaper & more effective
Stroke detection	It's an AI-based device that identifies strokes before physicians can, cutting down the time for analysis and saving patients' lives earlier.
Breast cancer detection	Physicians now use deep learning technologies to treat and diagnose cancer, which is much more effective than regular treatments.

AI has proven particularly effective for diagnosing complex and potentially serious diseases, with cardiology being a significant area of interest. The study shows how quickly AI research is being used to diagnose diseases; from 1% in 2009 to 20% in 2019, the proportion of papers that deal with this topic has increased [67]. This increase highlights how AI is becoming more critical in early disease diagnosis and how it might improve diagnostic procedures.

3. Current application of AI in healthcare

One current AI application in global healthcare predicts newly emergent COVID-19 hotspots by fusing contact tracing with aircraft passenger data. Contact tracing entails informing those subjected to quarantine to stop the spread of illness. Together, Google and Apple are developing an AI-powered contact tracking tool via smartphone APIs. Users may submit lab results using this system, and location services assist in finding and alert anyone who could have been near an infected individual [2].

Canadian company BlueDot develops software to evaluate outbreak risks and lower exposure to infectious illnesses. Their groundbreaking work used automated surveillance, ML, and NLP to anticipate the global spread of COVID-19 accurately. To predict epidemics, they analyze a large amount of data daily, including travel information, worldwide news, temperature, and animal data. Table 3 highlights some of the most cutting-edge AI technologies [16].

Table 2. Current advanced applications of AI in healthcare [70-77].

Current AI applications	How they work	Images
Zip up healing	They function similarly to stitches but are less unpleasant. They seal wounds without the need for needles and speed up healing. Yet, they won't replace conventional sutures for large wounds.	
AI assistant wearable for talking	It's for people who cannot speak and have vocal cord problems. This device detects the movement of the vocal cord muscle and converts it into speech using ML technology.	
At-home DIY ultrasound breast monitoring	Women can do their breast cancer examination at home. It is a tiny device that you just need to move around your chest, and it creates ultrasound images and detects if anything is there. It is a quick check without having to go to the doctor.	
Non invasive CRP monitoring from sweat	It is a tiny chip-type device that monitors the CRP level in sweat if it is stuck to your skin. This device easily identifies COPD and heart failure without even having to go to the physician for examination.	
Healing chronic wounds with electricity	Providing a controlled electric field to the wounded place can significantly reduce the wound without surgery or for wounds that are difficult to treat.	

The Future of Artificial Intelligence in Medicine: Present Realities and Future Considerations in Cardiology, Radiology and Ophthalmology

<p>Drone delivered defibrillators</p>	<p>These drones reach the emergency site with the emergency machine even before the ambulance arrives, saving many lives.</p>	
<p>Disney's Holo tile floor for rehabilitation</p>	<p>The technology allows users to seamlessly walk, run, and move in any direction while in a VR environment, allowing older adults to exercise without the risk of falling or getting injured by gym equipment.</p>	

Specific uses of AI in healthcare

Various innovations in AI in healthcare provide more efficient treatment to patients. These cutting-edge technologies strive to improve patient experiences and increase access to healthcare for all people worldwide. It also aligns with the UN's Sustainable Development Goals. AI technologies that are implemented correctly can eliminate human involvement as well. To assist in defining the study's scope and bolstering the development of an all-encompassing legal framework for AI regulation, Table 4 enumerates particular AI uses in the healthcare industry.

Table 3. Some examples of AI in healthcare [17].

AI applications in healthcare
1. Care management
2. Medical imaging analysis
3. Drug discovery
4. Forecasting kidney disease
5. Researching and treating cancer
6. Precision medicine
7. AI-based diagnostic

AI has the potential to drastically cut costs in the healthcare industry while improving patient care in several crucial applications [17]:

Error Reduction and Enhanced Care: AI can reduce human error and increase care management by providing sophisticated analytical skills [18].

Medical Imaging Analysis: AI helps radiologists evaluate pictures from CT, MRI, ultrasound, and other modalities. It helps in improving the diagnosis of diseases like lung cancer and brain tumors from images by pointing out anomalies [19,20].

Chronic Kidney Disease: By evaluating medical data from lab tests and electronic health records, artificial intelligence (AI) can forecast the likelihood and course of chronic kidney disease. It can aid in the early diagnosis and treatment of acute renal damage [26,27].

Cancer Research and Therapy: AI advances cancer research by enhancing diagnosis, prognosis, and therapy approaches. It also helps with early disease identification and improves treatment by analyzing genetic, histopathological, and clinical data to improve cancer therapy [28-31].

Drug creation and Discovery: AI aids in generating novel theories and identifying possible therapies by evaluating massive datasets from genetic, molecular, and clinical sources. Academics and pharmaceutical corporations increasingly use AI to increase drug creation and repurposing [21-25].

AI-powered precision medicine customizes treatments for each patient by analyzing their genetic and health profiles. It facilitates modified wellness-focused treatment, forecasts medication reactions, and optimizes doses according to patients' needs [32,33].

AI's application in healthcare can enhance effectiveness, accuracy, and patient outcomes in several fields.

4. A peek at the future: The impact of AI on the delivery of healthcare

Artificial intelligence (AI) will dramatically change healthcare operations and delivery. Virtual health assistants with AI capabilities can improve patient care by scheduling appointments, providing individualized health information, responding to patient inquiries, and tracking health indicators. With this technology, patients have greater access to resources, experience lower healthcare expenditures, and gain more control over their health.

In telemedicine, AI makes diagnosing and monitoring patients remotely more accessible by recording vital signs, analyzing real-time data, and looking for patterns or abnormalities. This leads to better patient outcomes, fewer hospital readmissions, and early intervention. Furthermore, AI-driven triage systems may efficiently prioritize patient treatment, improving the telemedicine services' overall effectiveness [35].

AI-driven predictive analytics is revolutionizing healthcare by facilitating early intervention through risk assessment. Artificial Intelligence (AI) can improve health outcomes and save costs by providing personalized health recommendations based on the analysis of extensive patient data, including genetics, lifestyle, and environment.

Robotic equipment with AI capabilities boosts surgical results and precision while lowering complications. AI advances data-driven decision-making, which improves care coordination, therapy selection, and diagnosis accuracy. AI has the potential to completely transform population health management by identifying inequalities, maximizing the use of available resources, and implementing focused treatments.

However, resolving ethical issues like privacy and human-machine collaboration is necessary before implementing AI into healthcare. Improving patient care and changing healthcare delivery must balance AI innovation and a human-centered strategy. To fully realize AI's promise in healthcare, cooperation between technologists, patients, legislators, and healthcare practitioners is essential [36].

Figure 3. Comparison of Traditional Methods and ML-based Prognostic Models for Disease Progression [78].

How to build Artificial Intelligence into a healthcare foundation

AI faces several challenges in becoming a foundational element in healthcare. These challenges include accessing relevant data, concerns about implementing AI in clinical settings, and ethical dilemmas that must be addressed [37]. One way to have data privacy is to allow people a choice not to use ML systems if they have any insecurities about sharing their health data with a machine [38]. Moreover, providing stricter data security, such as by adding data encryption and adopting federated learning techniques, is necessary to protect privacy and address ethical concerns surrounding AI use in healthcare [37][39][40].

Patients must also be informed when AI processes their data and consent to its use for machine learning applications, as shown in the figure below. Furthermore, ensuring accountability for AI decisions is crucial. Implementing rigorous regulations, conducting regular audits, and validation processes can help establish accountability and foster the development of human-centered AI systems [41][42]. While AI advancements promise to reduce errors in healthcare, there's a risk of overreliance on AI, potentially diminishing personal decision-making [43]. Proper training for healthcare professionals is essential to minimize or eliminate this risk and ensure accurate disease screening and treatment [44].

Healthcare professionals should get an AI education to integrate AI tools. This will increase their productivity while building on their knowledge and experience. Clinicians can increase their productivity even more using AI systems in the information processing sector [45][46]. Below, you can see a model of AI reaching the hands of users from experts in the healthcare sector.

Figure 4. Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare: Foundation [79].

5. AI'S PROMISE FOR MODERN MEDICINE

The abundance of healthcare data accessible, the accessibility of low-cost, high-level computer power, the extensive usage of electronic medical records (EMRs), and broader advancements in computing technology are the main drivers of recent progress in AI in medicine.

Radiology, pathology, ophthalmology, and cardiology are just a few medical specialties that stand to gain significantly from artificial intelligence. AI in medicine is still in the trial stage but has enormous potential to improve clinical procedures. Artificial intelligence (AI) enables clinicians to monitor patient health more effectively by integrating and analyzing data from several sources, including home monitors and activity trackers.

Diagnostic Radiology

By analyzing massive datasets to extract insightful information, AI, in particular ML and deep learning (DL), has the potential to revolutionize diagnostic imaging and pathology. Radiology procedures are anticipated to improve by incorporating AI and DL technology into routine clinical imaging. Complex information is frequently taken from MRIs, CT scans, and X-rays. This process makes it challenging and time-consuming for human radiologists to interpret. However, by using AI with feature selection, extraction, and identification of disease patterns from medical pictures, radiologists can make better decisions in enhancing patient recovery. Clinicians collaborate with these technologies to provide more efficient care to the patient.

Figure 5. AI Integration for Automatic Medical Image Interpretation [78].

Cardiology

The field of cardiology is dependent on many factors of a patient's health. This can include a patient's weight, body mass index (BMI), low-density lipoprotein (LDL) levels, high-density lipoprotein levels, blood pressure and analysis of electrocardiogram (EKG) data. Artificial intelligence can currently be used to take into account the aforementioned patient's data and use it to predict risk of myocardial infarction (heart attack), heart failure and other heart diseases. Additionally, AI tools are now being increasingly used to analyze EKG data which some doctors may miss through analysis with the naked eye.

AI can improve the diagnostic accuracy and even serve as a second set of eyes to analyze EKGs. This will lead to the more accurate diagnosis of conditions such as arrhythmias, heart failure, coronary artery disease and other heart related diseases. As the AI tool continues to develop AI may be able to develop into a tool that is more advanced than the highest trained doctors in analysis of EKGs and predicting risk of disease through evaluation of risk factors.

Today, there are also applications of AI in monitoring of heart health in real time. Smart watches and devices can now track key heart data in real time such as heart rate, blood pressures and even EKG data. This gives physicians increased and live data regarding a patient's health. AI will also be key to clinical research in the field of cardiology as it can be used to analyze large sets of data and be used in clinical trials to assist in drug discovery to treat-diseases.

Pathology

In pathology, the diagnosis of bio specimens has historically depended on the pathologist's skill. In this area, deep learning algorithms are shown to be quite helpful. For instance, a Google-developed DL-based convolutional neural network (CNN) has shown accuracy in identifying metastatic breast cancer in lymph node tissue, matching that of human pathologists.

However, this is becoming less common as new genomic and biomarker data become available, the disease becomes more complex, and fewer medical students choose to specialize in pathology. AI systems are not exhausted by analyzing innumerable specimen slides, but human pathologists could find it challenging to spot minute cancer deposits. Additionally, pathologists find it simpler to remain up to date with breakthroughs by managing the increasing amount of genetic data and novel biomarkers using ML.

Ophthalmology

Ophthalmology practices increasingly integrate ML and DL to take care of retinal diseases. One notable achievement is the FDA approval of an AI-based device for detecting diabetic retinopathy. Schlegl et al. pioneered a deep learning system that automatically identifies and quantifies intraretinal cystoid fluid (IRC) and subretinal fluid (SRF). This system can accurately categorize fluid patterns caused by wet age-related macular degeneration (AMD) and retinal vein occlusion (RVO).

According to research, deep learning in retinal image analysis offers a precise method for distinguishing between different types of retinal fluid across various exudative muscular diseases and optical coherence tomography (OCT) devices [52]. Below, we can see a figure of people with macular degeneration-related visual impairment who can customize the Oculenz Augmented Reality Headset to project images onto their functioning retina.

Figure 6. People with macular degeneration-related visual impairment who can customize the Oculenz Augmented Reality Headset to project images onto their functioning retina [81].

6. CONSIDERING THE FUTURE

Although it is difficult to forecast how AI will affect medicine in the future, AI will undoubtedly play a significant role in the medical field. Artificial intelligence (AI) systems, like IBM Watson, are more intelligent than humans. They can process and hold a vast amount of data and medical literature, making it a wealth of information for the world. For example, AI can remember all the pros and cons of any medication or treatment that a physician might not recognize.

AI and augmented reality applications can improve surgical accuracy. AI helps find illness by seeing symptoms and analyzing the dataset and associated risks. Examples include comparing heart attack and stroke risk variables and assessing cancer risks. AI is predicted to improve medical practice over time by avoiding diseases, minimizing adverse side effects, and eliminating pointless testing, which will benefit patients, their families, and the healthcare system as a whole [53].

In Table 4 below, you can see the top AI-based medical trends in 2024 that are helping physicians and patients take the healthcare sector a few steps ahead using AI [2].

Table 4. Top trends in the future of medicine and healthcare [2].

The Future of Artificial Intelligence in Medicine: Present Realities and Future Considerations in Cardiology, Radiology and Ophthalmology

AI Trends	Used for	Purpose
Rise of generative AI platforms	Used for chronic disease patient management	They help patients by answering patients' queries about diseases & giving them suggestions on how to improve their lifestyle
Blood pressure revolution	Technologies like smartwatches and skin patches	People with high or low blood pressure can constantly monitor and work on their blood pressure without having to visit an expert for a checkup now and then.
AI digital twins	AI imitates a person, talking in a different language that the person doesn't know to communicate with someone else on that person's behalf.	Physicians use AI to provide telemedicine by talking to patients in the language patients know, but the physicians don't. AI twins imitate the physicians and translate what the physicians say to the patients in a video or a call.
Blood testing reimaged	Made to be used by patients at home	They are microtrends built by companies so patients can easily take their saliva or blood at home and do the testing. For example, during the pandemic, people did COVID-19 tests alone at home.
Multimodel LLM for clinicians	Used by the physicians to interact with all the other AI-based tools in the hospital for easy management	They will be used by physicians so that they can work with all the images and documents generated by AI-based tools without having to know how to operate each tool individually.
Evidence-based digital therapeutics	Technologies like apps, health-checking devices, and online services are now part of treatment.	Although physicians do not prescribe them, people use these apps or devices to check and manage their blood pressure or sugar levels.

Future challenges facing the field

There are still many discussions about the use of AI in medicine and how it can change the healthcare system. AI faces many technical obstacles when creating training datasets or building users' trust in AI systems. Lastly, there are significant ethical questions regarding equality and data usage in medical AI (Fig. 8).

Figure 7. Ethical challenges for AI in medicine [47].

Implementation challenges

Several limitations prevent medical AI datasets from being as helpful as they may be.

- Pathology cannot use AI because the data-collecting equipment becomes too expensive.
- Neural networks find it challenging to process pictures with billions of pixels. The images are huge, requiring huge memory.

This problem can be handled by reducing the size of the images, or we can break an image into smaller images and later merge them, which might jeopardize comprehensive analysis and detail [48,49].

Another major problem is labeling data for supervised learning. Because of the size of the datasets and time limits, medical experts frequently struggle to assign labels. Crowdsourced labeling raises privacy problems and may provide less accurate labels. This has sparked interest in enhancing labeling effectiveness and investigating unsupervised or poorly supervised learning techniques.

The performance of a can be highly affected by biases in technology and single source data. They both restrict the model's capacity to generalize across other data sources. It is important to verify using a variety of datasets and train onsite-specific data to improve generalization. Researchers must practice being cautious, as different label distributions might cause the model to learn incorrectly [50].

CONCLUSION

AI presents itself as a tool that will see increasing use in the field of Medicine particularly for physicians which are in surgery, cardiology, ophthalmology, radiology and improving clinical research through the use of electronic health record data of patients. All doctors will also benefit through the ability of AI to analyze patient data and enhance disease diagnosis and prevention strategies. The ethics of AI will also need to made clear as the field increases its use of AI technologies. Ensuring data confidentiality, proper use and autonomy the patients and their health record will be increasingly important as AI technologies continue to develop.

The Future of Artificial Intelligence in Medicine: Present Realities and Future Considerations in Cardiology, Radiology and Ophthalmology

Despite the ethical challenges, the opportunity to promote better health for all outweigh the ethical challenges of AI which can be protected through proper regulation and governance of medical AI and patient data. AI in the field of medicine presents itself as an opportunity to have disease diagnosis which is better than even the most experienced physicians, get years ahead of clinical research through implementation of AI algorithms in electronic health record data and a new tool for all physicians to help in the treatment of patients for the betterment of all of healthcare and all people's health.

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REFERENCES

- [1] PeerJ. "The impact of artificial intelligence in medicine on the future role of the physician." National Library of Medicine. 2019. doi:10.7717/peerj.7702.
- [2] Dr. Bertalan Mesko. Top 6 Medical Innovations to Watch For in 2024 - The Medical Futurist. Dec 21, 2023. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Hw_2983Gd-c
- [3] Achim Hekler, et al. "Superior skin cancer classification by the combination of human and artificial intelligence". Pubmed. 2019. DOI: 10.1016/j.ejca.2019.07.019
- [4] Andre Esteva, et al. "Dermatologist-level classification of skin cancer with deep neural networks". Pubmed. pp-115-118. 2017. doi: 10.1038/nature21056
- [5] Irfan Chaudhuri, Mark Tappan and Md. Shahidul Islam, Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Education: Present Realities and Future Considerations, J. Artificial Intelligence, 16 (1): 1-11, 2023. DOI: [10.3923/jai.2023.1.11](https://doi.org/10.3923/jai.2023.1.11)
- [6] Liam J Caffery, et al. "Transforming Dermatologic Imaging for the Digital Era: Metadata and Standards". pp-568-577. 2018. doi: 10.1007/s10278-017-0045-8.
- [7] Al Ali, R., Wardat, Y., & Al-Qahtani, M. "SWOM strategy and influence of its using on developing mathematical thinking skills and on metacognitive thinking among gifted tenth-grade students". Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education. 2023. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/12994>
- [8] Shrivastava, A., Suji Prasad, S. J., Yeruva, A. R., Mani, P., Nagpal, P., & Chaturvedi, A. "IoT Based RFID Attendance Monitoring System of Students using Arduino ESP8266 & Adafruit. io on Defined Area". Cybernetics and Systems, 1-12. 2023. Doi:10.1080/01969722.2023.2166243
- [9] Rashid, M. T., & Mahmud, S. A. "Intelligent seeker robot to locate dead bodies and survivors under debris". In 2017 IEEE Global Humanitarian Technology Conference (GHTC). pp. 1-6. 2017. doi: 10.1109/GHTC.2017.8239345
- [10] Bansal, T., Gunasekaran, K., Wang, T., Munkhdalai, T., & McCallum, A. "Diverse distributions of self-supervised tasks for meta-learning in NLP". arXiv preprint arXiv:2111.01322. 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2111.01322>
- [11] Hussain, H. K., Tariq, A., & Gill, A. Y. "Role of AI in Cardiovascular Health Care; a Brief Overview". Journal of World Science, 2(4), 794-802. 2023. Doi: 10.58344/jws.v2i4.284
- [12] Davenport TH. "The AI Advantage". Cambridge: MIT Press. 2018. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15228053.2020.1756084>
- [13] Ursula Schmidt-Erfurth, et al. "Machine learning to analyze the prognostic value of current imaging biomarkers in neovascular age-related macular degeneration". Ophthalmology Retina. 2018. Pp:24-30. Doi: 10.1016/j.oret.2017.03.015
- [14] Rajkomar A, Oren E, Chen K, et al. "Scalable and accurate deep learning with electronic health records". npj Digital Medicine. 2018. Doi: 10.1038/s41746-018-0029-1

- [15] David W Shimabukuro. Et al. “Effect of a machine learning-based severe sepsis prediction -algorithm on patient survival and hospital length of stay: a -randomised clinical trial”. *BMJ Open Respir Res.* 2017. Doi: 10.1136/bmjresp-2017-000234
- [16] Isaac I Bogoch et al. “Pneumonia of unknown aetiology in Wuhan, China: Potential for international spread via commercial air travel”. *J Travel Med.* 2020. Doi: 10.1093/jtm/taaa008
- [17] Sunarti S, Rahman FF, Naufal M, Risky M, Febriyanto K, Masnina R. “Artificial intelligence in healthcare: opportunities and risk for future”. *Gac Sanit* 35(Supplement 1):S67–S70. 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaceta.2020.12.019>
- [18] Klumpp M, Hintze M, Immonen M, Ródenas-Rigla F, Pilati F, Aparicio-Martínez F, Çelebi D, Liebig T, Jirstrand M, Urbann O, Hedman M, Lipponen JA, Bicciato S, Radan AP, Valdivieso B, Thronicke W, Gunopulos D, Delgado-Gonzalo R. “Artificial Intelligence for Hospital Health Care: Application Cases and Answers to Challenges in European Hospitals”. *Healthcare* 9(8):961. 2021. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9080961>
- [19] Hosny A, Parmar C, Quackenbush J et al. “Artificial intelligence in radiology”. *Nat Rev Cancer* 18:500–510. 2018. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41568-018-0016-5>
- [20] Chiu H-Y, Chao H-S, Chen Y-M. “Application of Artificial Intelligence in Lung Cancer”. *Cancers* 14(6):1370. 2022. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers14061370>
- [21] Paul D, Sanap G, Shenoy S, Kalyane D, Kalia K, Tekade RK. “Artificial intelligence in drug discovery and development”. *Drug Discov Today* 26(1):80–93. 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drudis.2020.10.010>
- [22] Quazi S. “Artificial intelligence and machine learning in precision and genomic medicine”. *Med Oncol* 39(8):120. 2022. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12032-022-01711-1>
- [23] Chafai N, L Bonizzi, S Botti & B Badaoui. “Emerging applications of machine learning in genomic medicine and healthcare, *Critical Reviews in Clinical Laboratory Sciences*”. 2023. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408363.2023.2259466>
- [24] Zhou Y, Wang F, Tang J, Nussinov R, Cheng F. “Artificial intelligence in COVID-19 drug repurposing”. *Lancet Digital Health* 2(12):e667–e676. 2020. Doi: 10.1016/S2589-7500(20)30192-8
- [25] Floresta G, Zagni C, Gentile D, Patamia V, Rescifina A. “Artificial Intelligence Technologies for COVID-19 De Novo Drug Design”. *Int J Mol Sci* 23(6):3261. 2022. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23063261>
- [26] Zhu Y, Bi D, Saunders M et al. “Prediction of chronic kidney disease progression using recurrent neural network and electronic health records”. *Sci Rep* 13:22091. 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-49271-2>
- [27] Tomašev N, Glorot X, Rae JW et al. “A clinically applicable approach to continuous prediction of future acute kidney injury”. *Nature* 572:116–119. 2019. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1390-1>
- [28] Chen Z-H, Lin L, Wu C-F, Li C-F, Xu R-H, Sun Y. “Artificial intelligence for assisting cancer diagnosis and treatment in the era of precision medicine”. *Cancer Commun* 41:1100–1115. 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cac2.12215>
- [29] Johnson M, Albizri A, Simsek S. “Artificial intelligence in healthcare operations to enhance treatment outcomes: a framework to predict lung cancer prognosis”. *Ann Oper Res* 308:275–305. 2022. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-020-03872-6>
- [30] Bera K, Schalper KA, Rimm DL et al. “Artificial intelligence in digital pathology — new tools for diagnosis and precision oncology”. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol* 16:703–715. 2019. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41571-019-0252-y>
- [31] Huynh E, Hosny A, Guthrie C et al. “Artificial intelligence in radiation oncology”. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol* 17:771–781. 2020. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41571-020-0417-8>
- [32] Yurkovich JT, Evans SJ, Rappaport N et al. “The transition from genomics to phenomics in personalized population health”. *Nat Rev Genet.* 2023. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41576-023-00674-x>

The Future of Artificial Intelligence in Medicine: Present Realities and Future Considerations in Cardiology, Radiology and Ophthalmology

- [33] de Jong J, Cutcutache I, Page M, Elmoufti S, DilleJongy C, Fröhlich H, Armstrong M. “Towards realizing the vision of precision medicine: AI based prediction of clinical drug response”. *Brain* 144(6):1738–1750. 2021. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awab108>
- [34] Alarabi, K., & Wardat, Y. “UAE-based teachers’ hindsight judgments on physics education during the COVID-19 pandemic”. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 58(3), 2497-2511. 2021. Doi: 10.17762/pae.v58i3.4283
- [35] Shams, A. T., & Akter, S. “Eco-Centric Versus Anthropocentric Approach in Literary Pedagogy: Inclusion of Non-Human Narratives as Teaching Social Justice”. 2022. Doi: DOI:10.17406/GJHSS
- [36] Jiang F, Jiang Y, Zhi H, et al. “Artificial intelligence in healthcare: past, present and future *Stroke and Vascular Neurology*”. 2017;2. doi: 10.1136/svn-2017-000101
- [37] Khan B, Fatima H, Qureshi A, et al. “Drawbacks of artificial intelligence and their potential solutions in the healthcare sector”. *Biomed Mater Devices*. 2023. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44174-023-00063-2>
- [38] Honkela A, Das M, Nieminen A, Dikmen O, Kaski S. “Efficient differentially private learning improves drug sensitivity prediction”. *Biol Direct*. 2018. Doi: 10.1186/s13062-017-0203-4
- [39] Sheller MJ, Edwards B, Reina GA, et al. “Federated learning in medicine: facilitating multi-institutional collaborations without sharing patient data”. *Sci Rep*. 2020. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-020-69250-1
- [40] Rischke R, Schneider L, Müller K, et al. “Federated learning in dentistry: chances and challenges”. *J Dent Res*. 2022. DOI: 10.1177/00220345221108953
- [41] Ueda D, Kakinuma T, Fujita S, et al. “Fairness of artificial intelligence in healthcare: review and recommendations”. *Jpn J Radiol*. 2024. DOI: 10.1007/s11604-023-01474-3
- [42] White T, Blok E, Calhoun VD. “Data sharing and privacy issues in neuroimaging research: opportunities, obstacles, challenges, and monsters under the bed”. *Hum Brain Mapp*. 2022. DOI: 10.1002/hbm.25120
- [43] Stewart J, Freeman S, Eroglu E, et al. “Attitudes towards artificial intelligence in emergency medicine”. *Emerg Med Australas*. 2023. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1742-6723.14345>
- [44] Zech JR, Badgeley MA, Liu M, et al. Variable generalization performance of a deep learning model to detect pneumonia in chest radiographs: a cross-sectional study. *PLoS Med*. 2018. Doi: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1002683
- [45] Ahmed SK, Hussein S, Chandran D, Islam MR, Dhama K. The role of digital health in revolutionizing healthcare delivery and improving health outcomes in conflict zones. *Digit Health*. 2023. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/20552076231218158>
- [46] Islam MR, Urmi TJ, Mosharrafa RA, Rahman MS, Kadir MF. Role of ChatGPT in health science and research: A correspondence addressing potential application. *Health Sci Rep*. 2023. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/hsr2.1625>
- [47] Pranav Rajpurkar, Emma Chen, Oishi Banerjee and Eric J. Topol. “AI in health and medicine”. *Nature medicine*. 2022. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-021-01614->
- [48] Courtiol, P. et al. “Deep learning-based classification of mesothelioma improves prediction of patient outcome”. *Nat. Med*. 2019. Pp-1519–1525. Doi: DOI: 10.1038/s41591-019-0583-3
- [49] Van der Laak, J., Litjens, G. & Ciompi, F. Deep learning in histopathology: the path to the clinic. *Nat. Med*. 2021. Pp-775–784. Doi: DOI: 10.1038/s41591-021-01343-4
- [50] Willemink, M. J. et al. “Preparing medical imaging data for machine learning”. *Radiology*. 2020. Pp-4–15. DOI: 10.1148/radiol.2020192224
- [51] Liew C. “The future of radiology augmented with Artificial Intelligence: a strategy for success”. *European Journal of Radiology* 102. 2018. Pp-152–156. DOI 10.1016/j.ejrad.2018.03.019.
- [52] Schlegl T, Waldstein SM, Bogunovic H, Endstraßer F, Sadeghipour A, Philip AM, Podkowinski D, Gerendas BS, Langs G, Schmidt-Erfurth U. “Fully automated detection and quantification of

- macular fluid in OCT using deep learning”. *Ophthalmology* 125. 2018. Pp-549–558 DOI 10.1016/j.ophtha.2017.10.031.
- [53] Abhimanyu S. Ahuja. “The impact of artificial intelligence in medicine on the future role of the physician”. *Peer J*. 2019. DOI 10.7717/peerj.7702
- [54] Verma AA, Murray J, Greiner R, et al. “Implementing machine learning in medicine”. *Canadian Medical Association Journal*. 2021. DOI:10.1503/cmaj.202434
- [55] Sunam Jassar, JD1; Scott J. Adams, MD2; Amy Zarzeczny, BA, LLB, LLM3; and Brent E. Burbidge, MD, FRCPC. “The future of artificial intelligence in medicine: Medical-legal considerations for health leaders”. *Healthcare Management Forum*. 2022. Vol. 35(3). Pp-185–189. DOI: 10.1177/08404704221082069
- [56] Kanagasingam, Y. et al. “Evaluation of artificial intelligence-based grading of diabetic retinopathy in primary care”. *JAMA Netw. Open* 1. 2018. doi: 10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2018.2665
- [57] Beede, E. et al. “A human-centered evaluation of a deep learning system deployed in clinics for the detection of diabetic retinopathy. in *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*”. Association for Computing Machinery. 2020. Doi:https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3313831.3376718
- [58] Gong, D. et al. “Detection of colorectal adenomas with a real-time computer-aided system (ENDOANGEL): a randomised controlled study”. *Lancet Gastroenterol. Hepatol*. 2020. Pp-352–361. doi: 10.1016/S2468-1253(19)30413-3
- [59] Wijnberge, M. et al. “Effect of a machine learning-derived early warning system for intraoperative hypotension vs. standard care on depth and duration of intraoperative hypotension during elective noncardiac surgery”. *J. Am. Med. Assoc*. 2020. Pp-1052–1060. doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.0592.
- [60] Wismüller, A. & Stockmaster, L. “A prospective randomized clinical trial for measuring radiology study reporting time on Artificial Intelligence-based detection of intracranial hemorrhage in emergent care head CT”. in *Medical Imaging 2020: Biomedical Applications in Molecular, Structural, and Functional Imaging* vol. 11317, 113170M (International Society for Optics and Photonics. 2020. Doi: https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2002.12515
- [61] Liu, X. et al. “Reporting guidelines for clinical trial reports for interventions involving artificial intelligence: the CONSORT-AI extension”. *Br. Med. J*. 2020. doi: https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m3164
- [62] Goldenberg SL, Nir G, Salcudean SE. “A new era: artificial intelligence and machine learning in prostate cancer”. *Nat Rev Urol*. 2019. Pp-391–403. Doi:https://doi.org/10.1038/s41585-019-0193-3.
- [63] Golden JA. “Deep learning algorithms for detection of lymph node metastases from breast Cancer: helping artificial intelligence be seen”. *JAMA*. 2017. pp-2184–6. Doi:https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2017.14580.
- [64] Somashekhar SP, Kumarc R, Rauthan A , et al . “Abstract S6-07: double blinded validation study to assess performance of IBM artificial intelligence platform, Watson for oncology in comparison with manipal multidisciplinary tumour board ? first study of 638 breast Cancer cases”. *Cancer Res*. 2017. doi:10.1158/1538-7445.SABCS16-S6-07
- [65] Esteva A, Kuprel B, Novoa RA, et al. “Dermatologist-level classification of skin Cancer with deep neural networks”. *Nature*. 2017. doi:10.1038/nature21056
- [66] Farina D, Vujaklija I, Sartori M, et al. “Man/machine interface based on the discharge timings of spinal motor neurons after targeted muscle reinnervation”. *Nat Biomed Eng*. 2017.doi:10.1038/s41551-016-0025
- [67] Simarjeet Kaur, et al. “Medical Diagnostic Systems Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) Algorithms: Principles and Perspectives”. *IEEE*. Vol 8. 2020. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3042273

The Future of Artificial Intelligence in Medicine: Present Realities and Future Considerations in Cardiology, Radiology and Ophthalmology

- [68] Matthias Klumpp, et al. “Artificial Intelligence for Hospital Health Care: Application Cases and Answers to Challenges in European Hospitals”. *Healthcare*. 2021, 9(8), pp-961; <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9080961>
- [69] Dr. Bertalan Mesko. Top 7 AI example in healthcare. Dec 7, 2022 <https://youtu.be/mkiDXTS6-mU?si=MxD3iCDIbYEXuHM9>
- [70] Dr. Bertalan Mesko. 7 Mindblowing Healthcare Innovations - The Medical Futurist. Jun 11, 2024. <https://youtu.be/IxyURkxkcSI?si=UmtwKzq-mmvjRfr3>
- [71] Disney unveiled the Holo Tile Floor! This cutting-edge multi-user. Michael Tanzillo on LinkedIn
- [72] Everdrone AB. Drone carrying a defibrillator saves its first cardiac arrest patient in Sweden
- [73] Science Brush. Healing chronic wounds three times faster with electricity
- [74] Researchers have created a wearable noninvasive sensor that monitor for a biomarker of inflammation in sweat. Wearable noninvasive sensor monitors sweat for signs of inflammation
- [75] A wearable ultrasound scanner could detect breast cancer earlier. MIT news
- [76] Speaking without vocal cords, thanks to a new AI-assisted wearable device. Tech Xplore
- [77] Zippers Instead of Sutures? This is Cool. | Orthopedics This Week. Orthopedics This Week.
- [78] Amina Catherine Ijiga, et al. “Precision healthcare analytics: Integrating ML for automated image interpretation, disease detection, and prognosis prediction”. *WJBPHS*. 2024. Pp-336–354. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2024.18.1.0214>
- [79] Patrick Glauner. “Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare: Foundations, Opportunities and Challenges”. *Digitalization in Healthcare*. 2021. Pp-1-15. DOI:10.1007/978-3-030-65896-0_1
- [80] Qin Pei, et al. “Artificial intelligence in clinical applications for lung cancer: diagnosis, treatment and prognosis”. *Clinical Chemistry and Laboratory Medicine (CCLM)*. 2022. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1515/cclm-2022-0291>
- [81] Ji-Peng Olivia Li, et al. “Digital technology, tele-medicine and artificial intelligence in ophthalmology: A global perspective”. *Prog Retin Eye Res*. 2021. doi: 10.1016/j.preteyeres.2020.100900

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